

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH
TERVALENT METALS. PART V.
THIOCYANATES OF CHRO-
MIUM BIGUANIDES.

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A new type of chromium bisbiguanide complex—diacido chromium bisbiguanide thiocyanate and nitrate—has been prepared and their properties studied. In addition, preparation and properties of chromium trisbiguanide hydroxo-thiocyanate, trithiocyanate and hydroxo-aquo-chromium bisbiguanide thiocyanate have been described.

In previous communications of this series various salts of chromium trisbiguanide and hydroxo-aquo-chromium bisbiguanide (Ray and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670; 1938, 15, 353; Ray and Ghosh, 1938, 15, 347, 350) have been described, excluding the thiocyanates. Attempts to prepare these latter have led to certain interesting results. When an aqueous solution of chromium trisbiguanide hydrate is treated with a solution of ammonium thiocyanate, the crystalline precipitate, which separates from the liquid, is a trisbiguanide hydroxo-thiocyanate with strongly alkaline character. From the filtrate neutral bright red crystals of a substance containing two biguanide molecules and three thiocyanate radicals per chromium atom separate after some time. The only possible constitution for a compound of this composition, in keeping with the hexa co-ordination of chromic chromium, is given by

in which the central chromium atom has two of its primary valencies satisfied by combination with two biguanide molecules as usual, while its third primary valency binds one of the thiocyanate radicals inside the complex zone. The other thiocyanate radical in the same zone is really a negative ion, with its positive counterpart represented by a $-\text{NH}_2^+$ group of one of the biguanide molecules, and is linked co-ordinatively to the central chromium atom through nitrogen. This is illustrated by the following figure :

The substance, however, gradually hydrolyses in aqueous solution into aquo-compounds to form mono- and diaquo-chromium bisbiguanide thiocyanate as indicated by the cryoscopic and conductivity measurements. Silver nitrate precipitates practically the whole of the thiocyanate from the solution at the room temperature. At lower temperatures (10-15°) a part of the thiocyanate, however, remains in the solution. Cryoscopic measurement for the molecular weight gives a value (170) which is lower than half (214) but greater than one-third (142.6) of the formula weight. Conductivity measurements at 15°, however, furnishes evidence of considerable hydrolysis of the diaquo-derivative. The aqueous solution of the is also slightly acid to litmus as could be expected from the formation of an aquo-salt.

Attempts to prepare the corresponding nitrate by double decomposition with silver nitrate led only to the diaquo-nitrate—an evidence for the hydrolytic dissociation of the thiocyanate. But this diaquo-nitrate is salt converted into dinitrato-chromium bisbiguanide nitrate by losing water at 125°.

The hydrolysis of the salt can, therefore, be represented as :

In addition to this chromium bisbiguanide thiocyanate, which represents a new type (diacido) of bisbiguanide series, chromium trisbiguanide trithiocyanate and hydroxo-thiocyanate, as well as hydroxo-aquo-chromium bisbiguanide thiocyanate have been described in this paper,

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chromium trisBiguanide Hydroxo-thiocyanate.—When a strong ice-cold solution of chromium *trisbiguanide* hydroxide was treated with a strong solution of ammonium thiocyanate in excess, a dull red crystalline precipitate separated gradually on stirring. This was filtered off, as it was found to be a mixture of two or more products, possibly of chromium *trisbiguanide* dihydroxo-monothiocyanate and monohydroxo-dithiocyanate, which could not be separated by recrystallisation. The filtrate from the above precipitate was allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature, when a second crop of purer monohydroxo-dithiocyanate was obtained in the form of dull red crystals. These were filtered, washed first with a little ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The crystals were afterwards dried in an atmosphere free from CO₂ over moist NaOH,

The reaction occurs probably as follows.

{Found: N, 47'25 ; S, 12'70 ; Cr, 10'50. [Cr, (BigH⁺)₃]_{(SCN)₂}^(OH) · H₂O requires N, 47'0 ; S, 12'60 ; Cr, 10'30 per cent.}

The substance forms dull red crystals, moderately soluble in water and strongly alkaline to litmus. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts on warming.

Chromium bisBiguanide Trithiocyanate.—This new type of compound was obtained from the filtrate of the above described hydroxo-thiocyanate on keeping for a few days. The same substance was also obtained directly by heating on the water-bath a mixture of concentrated solutions of chromium *trisbiguanide* hydroxide and ammonium thiocyanate till all free ammonia escaped from the solution. The latter was then kept in a desiccator over concentrated H₂SO₄ when the *bisbiguanide* trithiocyanate separated in beautiful red crystals. These were washed first with little ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The crystals, thus obtained, were quite pure. In some preparations they were recrystallised from a little water. These were dried in air.

The reaction may be represented as follows:

{Found: N, 42'85, 43'1; S, 22'3, 22'2; Cr, 12'3, 12'35.

$[(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Cr} \cdot \overset{\text{SCN}}{\text{NCS}}^-] \text{SCN}$ requires N, 42'50; S, 22'40; Cr, 12'15 per cent}.

The substance is readily soluble in water and reacts very slightly acid to litmus. From a cold concentrated solution, the whole of the thiocyanate is not immediately precipitated by silver nitrate. Hydrolysis, however, occurs readily in aqueous solution on dilution or warming, as indicated by the cryoscopic and conductivity measurements.

Cryoscopic measurement.

Substance, (g/100 c.c.)	Depression. Δ	Mol. wt. m	Vant Hoff's factor $i = M/m$.
0'7418	0'078	171'2	2'5
0'3709	0'040	167'0	2'56

$M = \text{mol. wt. calculated} = 428.$

The result seems to suggest a partial hydrolysis into:

Molecular conductivity.

($t = 18^\circ$).

v (dilution)	32	64	128	256	512	1024
μ	188'0	216'2	230'0	248'2	271'5	276'6

Molecular conductivity at 25° for μ_{1000} of $[\text{Cr}(\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2)_3] (\text{SCN})_3$ and $[(\text{NH}_3)_4 \cdot \text{Cr} \cdot \overset{\text{OH}_2}{\text{Cl}}] (\text{NO}_3)_2$ are respectively 325'5 and 260'3 (Werner and Kalkmann, *Annalen*, 1902, 322, 313; Werner and Miolati, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 14, 515).

Taking note of the difference in temperatures, it may, therefore, be concluded that the substance hydrolyses more or less completely at 18° into the diaquo-derivative $[(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Cr} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] (\text{SCN})_3$.

Chromium bisBiguanide Trinitrate and its Diaquo-derivative.

Finely powdered chromium bisbiguanide trithiocyanate (2'5 g.) was made into a paste with water and the solution of a calculated quantity (3 g.) of silver nitrate in a little water was added, drop by drop, to the paste,

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agitating or shaking the mixture all the time. The precipitate of silver thiocyanate was filtered off. The filtrate was kept overnight in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 . The concentrated solution, when cooled in ice, deposited crystals of brick-red colour. These were filtered, washed first with a little ice-cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. {Found : N, 36.90; Cr, 10.75. $[(BigH^+)_2 \cdot Cr(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_3 \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 36.84; Cr, 10.52 per cent.}

Thus the fully hydrolysed or diaquo-derivative separates in the case of the nitrate. But the substance lost practically the whole of the water on heating to 120-125°. The loss of weight corresponded to 10.92%.

Calculated from the formula, $H_2O = 10.93\%$. The anhydrous compound gave on analysis N, 41.09.

$[(BigH^+)_2 \cdot Cr \begin{matrix} NO_3 \\ NO_3^- \end{matrix}]NO_3$ requires N, 41.36 per cent.

This shows that the hydrated diaquo-derivative, on losing water, is transformed into the chromium bisbiguanide trinitrate of the corresponding thiocyanate type, from which the diaquo-nitrate was obtained by double decomposition.

The anhydrous chromium bisbiguanide trinitrate, also brick-red in colour, very slowly absorbs water on exposure to air, changing gradually into the original diaquo-derivative after a long time.

Chromium trisBiguanide Trithiocyanate.

This normal salt was prepared by double decomposition from chromium trisbiguanide sulphate and barium thiocyanate. The finely powdered complex was agitated in a mortar with a concentrated solution of a calculated amount of barium thiocyanate. The solution, after the reaction was complete, must not contain any barium or sulphate ion. The filtrate from the barium sulphate was cooled in ice when dark red crystals of the normal thiocyanate separated from the solution. These were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. A second crop was obtained from the mother-liquor by evaporating over H_2SO_4 in vacuum.

The air-dried sample was analysed. {Found : N, 47.80; S, 18.28; Cr, 9.97. $[Cr(BigH^+)_3](SCN)_3$ requires N, 47.63; S, 18.15; Cr, 9.83 per cent.}

The substance forms bright red crystals, readily soluble in water. Cryoscopic measurement of aqueous solution indicates partial hydrolysis into bisbiguanide derivative. This accounts for the fact that the normal trisbiguanide trithiocyanate could not be obtained by the action of ammonium thiocyanate on trisbiguanide hydroxide.

Cryoscopic measurement.

Substance. (g/100 c.c.)	Depression. Δ	M. W. <i>m.</i>	Vant Hoff's factor $i = M/m$.
0.5355	0.081	119	4.45
0.26775	0.042	115	4.60

$M(\text{Calc. mol. wt.}) = 529.$

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bisBiguanide Thiocyanate.

The filtrate from the chromium trisbiguanide thiocyanate was allowed to remain at the ordinary temperature for some days, when the colour of the solution gradually changed from dark red to red-violet. This, on concentration in vacuum over H_2SO_4 and cooling in ice, gave red-violet crystals of the hydroxo-aquo complex. The crystals were washed first with a little ice-cold water and then with alcohol. For the purpose of analysis they were dried in air freed from CO_2 . {Found: N, 41.40; S, 15.80;

Cr, 13.0. $\left[(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Cr} \begin{array}{l} \cdot\text{OH} \\ \cdot\text{OH}_2 \end{array} \right] (\text{SCN})_2$ requires: N, 41.48; S, 15.80; Cr, 12.84 per cent.}

The substance is readily soluble in water forming a slightly alkaline solution like all hydroxo-aquo compounds previously described (*loc. cit.*).